

ments. Spectral measurements were carried out using a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer, a Beckman (Acculab T.M.10) ir spectrophotometer and a Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrometer with MVU-1.

Preparation and studies with thorium tungstate: Granulated TT suitable for column operation was prepared as follows. To a solution (100 ml) of 0.1 M $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ in 2 M HNO_3 kept at 80° , 0.1 M sodium tungstate solution (200 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The resulting fine white precipitate was washed with demineralised water until pH of the washing was around 2 and dried at room temperature over silica gel. The samples of TT were fused with caustic soda and the fused mass was leached with water and filtered. The total filtrate was analysed for tungsten by the usual procedure⁶. The precipitate was dissolved in 4 N HCl and the solution was analysed for thorium⁷. A weighed amount (0.5 g) of TT (sample no. 2) was immersed in a mixed solution (50 ml) of varying ratio of (NaCl+NaOH) with intermittent shaking for 48 h at 25° , the strength of Na^+ being fixed at 0.1 N. The capacity of the exchanger was determined by equilibrating TT (0.5 g) with 2 M NaCl solution (5.0 ml) for 48 h. Similar values for several uni- and bivalent cations were also determined. Ir spectra was measured by the KBr disk method and thermal analysis was carried out at a heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$. The radiation stability of the exchanger was tested by determining the ion-exchange capacity of the material before and after subjecting it to a γ -radiation doses upto a maximum total dose of 50 M rad in a GC-900 γ -chamber, at BARC, India. The chemical stability was measured by equilibrating the exchanger (0.5 g) into different solvents (50 ml) for 48 h and determining the tungsten content of the solution by the spectrophotometric method⁸. In order to examine the affinity of TT (sample no. 2) toward various metal ions, distribution coefficients

for several cations were determined by equilibrating the exchanger (0.5 g) with solutions (50 ml each) of cations for 48 h at room temperature with intermittent shaking. Fe^{III} , Zr^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Ce^{IV} and U^{VI} ions were determined spectrophotometrically⁸ and Hg by cold vapour AAS⁹. All other cations were determined by complexometric titration^{7,10,11}. For separation studies, glass columns (i.d., 1.5 cm) containing the ion-exchanger (5 g; 50–100 mesh) in the H^+ form were used.

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Antimony(III) Vanadate as an Inorganic Ion-exchanger†

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The only systematically studied antimony based exchanger is antimony(v) silicate¹. However, no information is available on the use of antimony(III) vanadate as an ion-exchanger. This communication summarises our findings on the synthesis, ion-exchange behaviour and analytical applications of antimony(III) vanadate.

Results and Discussion

Among the various samples prepared (Table 1), antimony(III) vanadate ($\text{Sb} : \text{V} = 1 : 1.4$) was used for the investigations. The effect of size and charge of the ingoing ion on the capacity of the exchanger for the alkali and alkaline earth metal ions were studied. The sequence shown by antimony(III) vanadate is as follows (exchange capacities given in

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TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF SYNTHESIS AND ION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF ANTIMONY(III) VANADATE

Sample no	Mixing ratio	Concn. of reagent (M)		pH	Mole ratio	i.e.c. in meq/g (dry weight)
		Sb ³⁺	VO ₃ ⁻			
1	1:1	0.05	0.1	1.18	1:1.4	0.90
2	1:1	0.1	0.1	1	1:2	0.75
3	1:1	0.05	0.05	0.95	1:1	0.65

parenthesis) : Mg²⁺ (0.55), Ca²⁺ (0.58), Sr²⁺ (0.62), Ba²⁺ (0.65), Li⁺ (0.75), Na⁺ (0.90), K⁺ (1.00).

Usually, at low aqueous concentrations and at ambient temperature, the extent of exchange increases with increasing valency of the ingoing ion², i.e. Ca²⁺>Na⁺. Antimony(III) vanadate does not show this sequence. The solubility products of the corresponding vanadates of the metal ions seem to be responsible for the unexpected departure from normal behaviour³. Such irregularities are not uncommon with inorganic ion-exchangers. Under similar condition for univalent ion the extent of exchange usually increases with decrease in size of the hydrated cation, i.e. K⁺>Na⁺>Li⁺. Antimony(III) vanadate follows this sequence. With the alkaline earth metal ion the extent of exchange decreases with increase of hydrated ionic radii. The exchanger is stable in water, alcohol, acetic acid, mineral acids upto 2.0 M and in 1.0 M solutions of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, CaCl₂ and BaCl₂.

The sample retains ion-exchange capacity even at 300°. The ion-exchange capacity decreases with increase of temperature. The exchanger can be regenerated upto four cycles without any appreciable loss in exchange capacity. The distribution study of 12 metal ions (Table 2) reveals that antimony(III)

TABLE 2—K_d VALUES (ml g⁻¹) OF METAL ION IN ANTIMONY(III) VANADATE DRIED AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Cation	Taken as	K _d ml g ⁻¹
Zn ²⁺	Sulphate	128.26
Mg ²⁺	Chloride	47.41
Ca ²⁺	Chloride	39.90
Pb ²⁺	Nitrate	Complete uptake
Hg ²⁺	Chloride	13.33
Cd ²⁺	Chloride	Complete uptake
Sn ²⁺	Chloride	Complete uptake
Cu ²⁺	Chloride	282.00
Co ²⁺	Chloride	Complete uptake
Ni ²⁺	Chloride	89.00
Bi ³⁺	Nitrate	4525.00
Th ⁴⁺	Nitrate	189.55

vanadate has high affinity for Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Sn²⁺, Co²⁺, Bi³⁺, Cu²⁺, Te⁴⁺ and Zn²⁺. It may be assumed that not only the ion-exchange reaction but also absorption and ion-sieve properties of the exchanger are responsible for the high uptake of these elements. The uptake of these ions is not a simple exchange but rather a process involving the introduction of ions in to the matrix of the sorbent³.

The effect of electrolyte (HNO₃, NH₄NO₃) concentrations on the distribution coefficient of some metal ions was studied. The uptake of ions as Cu, Th and Zn decreases with increase of electrolyte concentrations. As the ion-exchange material is stable in acids the exchange capacity is reduced in the presence of H⁺ and NH₄⁺ ions.

For separation studies the exchanger in the H⁺-form was taken in a glass column (30 cm×0.2 cm dia). The rate of flow in all separation was 0.5 ml min⁻¹. The separation of metal ions was tried with those for which the separation was greater than 5 (Table 2). The eluents were HNO₃, HCl and ammonium nitrate. In all separations the metal ion concentration was 0.005 M. For binary separation 10 ml each of the metal ion solution was used. The results of the binary and ternary separations are given in Table 3. The recovery

TABLE 3—BINARY AND TERNARY SEPARATIONS OF ANTIMONY(III) VANADATE COLUMNS

Separation	Eluent*	Amount of cation (mg)	
		Loaded	Recovered
Hg ²⁺ - Cd ²⁺	Hg ²⁺ +b	9.80	9.80
	Cd ²⁺ +a	5.62	5.60
Hg ²⁺ - Zn ²⁺	Hg ²⁺ +a	9.80	9.80
	Zn ²⁺ +d+g	3.52	3.51
Zn ²⁺ - Pb ²⁺	Zn ²⁺ +d+g	3.52	3.52
	Pb ²⁺ +e+h	10.10	10.05
Cu ²⁺ - Pb ²⁺	Cu ²⁺ +e+f	3.18	3.00
	Pb ²⁺ +e+h	10.10	10.10
Mg ²⁺ - Pb ²⁺	Mg ²⁺ +c+f	1.82	1.80
	Pb ²⁺ +e+h	10.10	10.00
Hg ²⁺ - Zn ²⁺ - Cd ²⁺	Hg ²⁺ +a	4.98	4.80
	Zn ²⁺ +d+g	1.76	1.70
	Cd ²⁺ +a	2.81	2.81
Hg ²⁺ - Mg ²⁺ - Pb ²⁺	Hg ²⁺ +a	4.90	4.90
	Mg ²⁺ +d+g	0.66	0.65
	Pb ²⁺ +e+h	5.05	4.98
	Hg ²⁺ +a	4.90	4.90
Hg ²⁺ - Mg ²⁺ - Cu ²⁺	Hg ²⁺ +a	4.90	4.90
	Mg ²⁺ +d+g	0.66	0.63
	Pb ²⁺ +e+h	1.59	1.58

*Eluents: ^a0.02 M HCl, ^b0.03 M HCl, ^c0.01 M HNO₃, ^d0.03 M HNO₃, ^e0.05 M HNO₃, ^f0.01 M NH₄NO₃, ^g0.03 M NH₄NO₃, ^h0.05 M NH₄NO₃.

ranged from 98 to 100% with variation of 1% for repetitive determinations. All the separations were carried out in neutral medium. A very interesting feature of the separations carried out (Table 3) is that the extent of separation of mercury from binary and ternary mixtures was 100% in most of the cases.

Experimental

Antimony(III) chloride and ammonium vanadate (Loba) were used. All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

Antimony(III) vanadate was prepared by adding ammonium vanadate solutions of various concentrations to acidic solutions of antimony(III) chloride with constant stirring under the condition given in Table 1. The pH was adjusted by adding